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THE SUCCESS FACTORS IN MERGER AND ACQUISITIONS (FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF MERGER AND ACQUISITION ADVISORY FIRMS)

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ABSTRACT

An entrepreneur may grow its business either by internal expansion or by external expansion. In the case of internal expansion, a firm grows gradually overtime in the normal course of the business, there acquisition of new assets replacement of the technology, obsolete equipment's. But in the external expansion acquires a running business and grows overnight through corporate combination these combination are in the form of merger and acquisition and playing an important role in the external organization. The main aim of the study is to study the success factors in mergers and acquisition because it has become a growing trend for companies, large, and small, domestic and foreign, to form a strategic alliance with particular industries. There are many specific goals that companies may be looking to achieve by doing this, but the main underlying reason is to guarantee the long term sustained achievement of fast profitable growth for their business. This paper is both descriptive and exploratory in nature both are chosen according to the requirement of the research both primary and secondary data are used for research and chi square is used as tool for the analysis

As expert advisory are sought in M&A activities to facilitate the undertaking and maximize the value of the transaction, advisory firms begin to play a more significant and at the same time lucrative role in M&A activities, to the extent of determining the outcome of such projects. Being an area of limited research, it is thus valuable to investigate what M&A advisory

firms view as critical success factors to the projects they undertake. Consequently, the research question of “What are the critical success factors for merger & acquisition projects in the view of merger & acquisition advisory firms” has been raised. A list of fifteen critical success factors for M&A projects is firstly identified from an extensive literature.

Keywords: M&A, Merger and Acquisitions, Factors, Strategies,

INTRODUCTION

India in the recent years has showed tremendous growth in the M&A deal. It has been actively playing in all industrial sectors. It is widely spreading far across the stretches of all industrial verticals and on all business platforms. The increasing volume is witnessed in various sectors like that of finance, pharmaceuticals, telecom, FMCG, industrial development, automotive and metals. The volume of M&A transactions in India has apparently increased to about 67.2 billion USD in 2010 from 21.3 billion USD in 2009. At present the industry is witnessing a whopping 270% increase in M&A deal in the first quarter of the financial year. This increasing percentage is mainly attributed to the increasing cross-border M&A transactions. Over that increasing interest of foreign companies in Indian companies has given a tremendous push to such transactions. Large Indian companies are going through a phase of growth as all are exploring growth potential in foreign markets and on the other end even international companies is targeting Indian companies for growth and expansion. Some of the major factors resulting in this sudden growth of merger and acquisition deal in India are favorable government policies, excess of capital flow, economic stability, corporate investments, and dynamic attitude of Indian companies.

Large Indian companies are going through a phase of growth as all are exploring growth potential in foreign markets and on the other end even international companies is targeting Indian companies for growth and expansion. Some of the major factors resulting in this sudden growth of merger and acquisition deal in India are favorable government policies, excess of capital flow, economic stability, corporate investments, and dynamic attitude of Indian companies. The recent merger and acquisition 2011 made by Indian companies worldwide are those of Tata Steel acquiring Corus Group plc, UK based company with a deal of US \$12,000 million and Hidalgo acquiring Novelis from Canada for US \$6,000 million With these major mergers and many more

on the annual chart, M&A services India is taking a revolutionary form. Creating a niche on all platforms of corporate businesses, merger and acquisition in India is constantly rising with edge over competition.

Mergers and acquisitions in the corporate world refer to the process of buying, selling or combining of different corporations to achieve rapid growth. In case of merger, two companies, often of same size, decide to go ahead as a single unit (new company) instead of operating separately. While, on the other hand, in case of acquisition, one organization takes over another to establish itself as the new owner of the business. Corporate mergers and acquisitions play pivotal role in the business and economy of any country. These result in significant restructuring of the industry and contribute substantially to the growth of the industry and economy of the country as well. Mergers and acquisitions are parts of corporate strategies that deal with buying / selling or combining of business entities, which in turn, help a company to grow quickly. However, merger and acquisition process is quite a complex process that consists of a few steps. Before going for any merger and acquisition, both the companies need to consider a few points and also need to go through some distinct steps. The merger and acquisition process is also a big point of concern for the companies involved in the deal, as the process could be full of risk and uncertainty. However, prior effective planning and research could make the process easy and simple.

Objectives of the Study

1. To find out the success criteria in the merger and Acquisition from the perspective of merger and acquisition firms
2. To find out the procedure and process of conducting the merger and acquisitions projects
3. To find out the role of merger and acquisitions advisory firm
4. To find out the reasons for the failure of merger and acquisitions projects

LITERATURE REVIEW

Mergers and acquisitions solely because of favorable capital market conditions. Firms are less likely to grow through mergers and acquisitions when stocks are booming. Aggregate financial market conditions do not impact on the nature of merger or acquisition. The relation between GDP growth and growth of firms through mergers and acquisitions is positive when firms seek immediate increases in production capacity in a growing economy. The desire for firm to grow through a merger or an acquisition might in turn be tempered by bad business conditions. In overall the empirical evidence between GDP growth and growth of firms through mergers and acquisitions is limited and mixed (Beckenstein, 1979). Industry variables are operational zed by assessing concentration and sales growth in the industry. According to Luypaert (2008). In highly concentrated industries, firms tend to recognize the impact of their polides and actions on one another. This could influence radiations to charges in competitive behavior like quantity restrictions, tacit collusion and horizontal mergers and acquisitions to increase the concentration within an industry which may help firms to realize market power. So, a positive relation between industry concentration and external growth may arise particularly in related mergers and acquisitions. Conversely, when the industry is already highly concentrated, it could have a lower incidence of mergers and acquisitions as them is less room left for further consolidation. Also, antitrust authorities may closely scrutinize newly planned deals when industries are already highly concentrated. Consistent with the latter arguments, Andrade and Stafford (2004) find that industry concentration has a negative impact on the decision to grow through mergers and acquisitions.

Mitchell and Mulherin (1996). Andrade and Stafford (2004), Powell and Yaws on (2005) have examined the effect of industry shocks on mergers and acquisitions activity across industries. They initially investigated through sales growth. Found that firms in mature or defining industries may want to shift their resources into growing industries, to guarantee their long-run survival hence existence of positive relationship between sales growth and mergers and acquisitions. Bidder variables are operational zed by assessing firm profitability which tends to positively influence mergers and acquisitions. Large and profitable firms often have or can better access financial resources that are needed to acquire other firms. More over large firms are expected to engage more in diversifying mergers and acquisitions as there may be few opportunities left for growth in their own industry ceteris paribus.

NEED OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of the study is to know the Success factors of Merger and Acquisitions from the perspective of merger and acquisition advisory firms. In a rapidly changing world, companies are facing unprecedented turmoil in global market, severe competition; rapid technological change and rising stock market volatility have increased the burden on managers to deliver superior performance and value for their shareholders. An increasing number of companies around the world are radically restructuring their assets, operations and business relationship with shareholders, creditors, and financial stakeholders. Corporate restructuring has facilitated thousands of organizations to reestablish their business and respond more quickly to new opportunities and expected challenges. In this situation the merger, acquisition and takeover has become the most potential strategy for the growth of the corporate world. The merger, acquisition and takeover is playing a very major role. The different companies adopt M&A is playing a very major role. The different companies adopt M&A for different for different reasons, the chief reasons are cost efficiency, revenue enhancement, tax gain, market share, market reputation, and to feel the presence in the new market. This paper is conducted to know the growth of merger and acquisition in the present arena how it is playing an important strategy in the corporate world.

Mergers

Investopedia.com⁴ defines merger as, ‘a merger involves the mutual decision of two companies to combine and become one entity; it can be seen as a decision made by two “equals”. The combined business, through structural and operational advantages secured by the merger, can cut costs and increase profits, boosting shareholder values for both groups of shareholders. A typical merger, in other words, involves two relatively equal companies, which combine to become one legal entity with the goal of producing a company that is worth more than the sum of its parts. In a merger of two corporations, the shareholders usually have their shares in the old company exchanged for an equal number of shares in the merged entity.’ At answer.com⁵, merger is defined as, ‘the statutory combination of two or more corporations in which one of the corporations survives and the other corporations cease to exist’. According to Machiraju (2003: 1), ‘merger is a broad term and it denotes the combination of two or more companies in such a

way that only one survives while the other is dissolved. A merger is an investment in a future growth opportunity. In merger proposals plant is ready and market acceptance, clear and well established. When two companies differ significantly in size, they usually merge’. Weston, Chung and Hoag 91996:4) define merger as, ‘any transaction that forms one economic unit from two or more previous ones’. McCarthy (1963:16) defines merger as, ‘the combination of two or more business entities into a single economic enterprise. To be more exact, however, the only type of business combinations that should be designated as mergers are statutory mergers or consolidations, i.e., when one or more companies are merged into another or into a new corporation in conformity with the statutes dealing with such transactions in the states of their incorporation’. According to De Pamphilis (2001:5), ‘mergers can be described from a structural or industrial-operational perspective.. From a structural standpoint a merger is a combination of two firms in which only one firm’s identity survives. A statutory merger is one in which the acquiring company assumes the assets and liabilities of the target company in accordance with the statutes of the state in which it is incorporated. A subsidiary merger of two companies occurs when the target becomes a subsidiary of the parent’.

Acquisitions

Investopedia.com⁶ defines acquisition as, ‘a takeover, or acquisition, is characterized by the purchase of a smaller company by a much larger one. This combination of “unequal’s” can produce the same benefits as a merger, but it does not necessarily have to be a mutual decision. A larger company can initiate a hostile takeover of a smallest firm, which essentially amounts to buying the company in the face of resistance from the smaller company’s management. Unlike in a merger, in an acquisition, the acquiring firm usually offers a cash price per share to the target firm’s shareholders or the acquiring firm’s shares to the shareholders of the target firm according to a specified conversion ratio. Either way, the purchasing company essentially finances the purchase of the target company, buying it outright for its shareholders’. At answer.com, acquisition⁷ is defined as, ‘the act of one corporation acquiring a controlling interest in another corporation’. According to Machiraju (2003:2), ‘the traditional acquisition is the negotiated acquisition in which a willing buyer and willing seller negotiate the terms under which an acquisition or merger occurs... Acquisition refers to a situation where one firm acquires another and the latter ceases to exist... A firm that attempts to acquire or merge with another company is

called an acquiring company. A target company is a firm that is being solicited by the acquiring company. The assets of the dissolved firm would be owned by the acquiring company. The shareholders of the acquired company are paid either cash or given shares in acquiring company'. McCarthy (1963:16) defined as, 'the act of one corporation acquiring a controlling interest in another corporation'. According to Machiraju (2003:2), 'the traditional acquisition is the negotiated acquisition in which a willing buyer and willing seller negotiate the terms under which an acquisition or merger occurs Acquisition refers to a situation where one firm acquires another and the latter ceases to exist. A firm that attempts to acquire or merge with another company is called an acquiring company. A target company is a firm that is being solicited by the acquiring company. The assets of the dissolved firm would be owned by the acquiring company. The shareholders of the acquired company are paid either cash or given shares in acquiring company'. Mc /cartgt (1963:16) defines acquisition as, 'a number of so-called mergers involving exchanges of capital stocks legally are acquisitions, particularly where there are large number of shareholders involved. In such non-merger cases, one company "acquires" the voting sock of another solely in exchange of its voting stock. Acquisitions, in a legal sense, may also be effected for cash or cash equivalent, such as debt securities'. According to De Pamphilis (2001:5), 'an acquisition occurs when one company takes a controlling stake in another firm, a legal subsidiary of another firm, or selected assets of another firm such as a manufacturing facility'.

EVOLUTION OF CRITICAL SUCCESS FACTORS

Research on CSF can be traced back to 1961, where Daniel (1961) first discussed "success factors" in management literature. In a broad approach, he focused on industry-related CSF which are relevant for any company in a particular industry Combining the perspective of both Daniel (1961) and Anthony et al. (1972), Rockart 91979) described a study on three organizations in 1979 which confirmed that organizations in the same industry may exhibit different CSF. The reasons for such a constellation are differences in geographic location and strategies among other factors. Nevertheless, Rockart was also able to identify analogies between the CSF lists of the three examined organizations: "it is noticeable that the first four factors on the mature clinic's list also appear on the other two lists. (...) These, it can be suggested, are the

all-encompassing industry-based factors. The remaining considerations, which are particular to one or the other of the practices but not to all, are generated by differences in environmental situation, temporal factors, geographic to location, or strategic situation.” (Rockart, 1979, p.87). In line with his initial study, Rockart (1982) gathered data in regard to IS executives. This data indicated that executives share a limited number of CSF. “Each executive (...) lists some, but not all, of the CSF gathered from the sample as a whole” (Zahedi, 1988, p.190). the remaining differences were linked to organizational aspects as well as the time pressure facing the particular manager at the time the data was collected (Rockart, 1982).

Furthermore, Rockart (1979) stressed that his approach did not attempt to address information needs related to the field of strategic planning. Instead, his CSF approach concentrates on information needs for management control and seeks to identify data which can be used to monitor and improve existing areas of business.

Table 1: showing the Development of Success Factors over time

Source	Critical Success Factors
(Ruben and Selling, 1967); Empirical	Technical performance as a measure of success. Project manager’s experience has minimal impact but the size of previously managed project t does affect t the manager’s performance
(Sayles & Chandler, 1971)	Project manager’s competence e; Scheduling ; Control systems and responsibilities; Monitoring and feedback; and Continuous involvement in the project t
(Martin, 1976)	Clear goals; Selection of project organizational philosophy; General management support; Organize and delegate authority; and Selection of project team.
(Baker, Murphy and fisher, 1983); Empirical	Clear goals; Goal commitment of project team; On-site project manager; Adequate funding to completion; Adequate project t team capability; Accurate initial cost estimates; Minimum start-up difficulties; Planning and control techniques; task-social orientation; and Absence of bureaucracy.
(Cleland and King, 1983)	Project summary; Operational concept; top management support; Financial support; Logistic requirements; Facility support; Market intelligence; Project schedule; Executive dev elopement and training; Manpower and organization; Acquisition; Information and communication channels; and Project review.
(Morris and Hughes, 1987); Empirical	Project objectives; Technical innovation uncertainty; Politics; Community involvement; Schedule duration urgency; Financial contract leg al problems; and implementation problems.
(Pinto and Slevin, 1987)	Project objectives, Top management support, project planning communication with client, human relations, technical tasks, client acceptance project control, communication and problem handling
(Tukel& Rom, 1995); Empirical	Top management support; Client consultation; Preliminary estimates; Availability of resources and Project managers’ performance.
(Pinto and Kharbanda, 1995)	Mission at the forefront; Early & Continual Client consultation; Technology; Scheduling system; Project team; Top Management Support and Continual ‘what if? Approach.

BACKGROUND OF CRITICAL SUCCESS FACTORS

Critical success factors (CSFs) are continually mentioned in relation to a project's successful outcome and also as factors that effect projects not achieving set objectives. Since the late 1960s, many theoretical and empirical studies have provided new lists of critical factors that have been developed throughout the literature relating to project success. With regards to CSFs, none have been cited more than Belassi and Tuckel (1996) who mention that the concentration of studies seem to focus on the generating of individual lists of factors that, if not considered or pre-determined, could lead to a project's failure. Previously, Pinto and Covin's (1989) research into CSFs highlights that as projects should be seen as unique, so to must the CSFs on each individual project.

The benefits of dealing with CSFs both before and at different stages of the Project Life Cycle (PLC) are discussed by several researches (Fortune and White, 2006; Pinto and Slevin, 1989; and Belassi and Tuckel, 1996). Within the extant literature, the close relationship of CSFs and success criteria is highlighted on numerous occasions (Chua et al, 1999; Davis, 2002 and Bryde, 2008). However, it was Pinto and Covin's (1989) research that was one of the first to establish that CSFs are more crucial at specific times during the PLC. From the earlier work of researchers such as Pinto and Covin (1989), it was possible for Fortune and White (2006) to create their Formal System Model that creates a structure in which CSFs can be addressed.

Capabilities and KSF in M&A

KSF are useful tool that can be controlled by management in order to achieve desirable outcomes (Rochart, 1979). Similarly, Turner (2004) claims that if KSF are adequately identified and controlled, the chances of success can be greatly increased. The topic of KSF has received significant interest in the last couple of decades especially when it turned into empirical research (Pinto and Prescott, 1990; KPMG, 1999; Bertoneclj and Kovac, 2007).

More KSF could mean higher degree of success in projects (Fortune and White, 2004). Additionally, Hoang and Lapumnuaypon (2008) suggest that KSF developed later are more

complex than those of the previous decade since more recent success factors cover both hard and soft aspects.

Soft issues should be carefully considered, as human capital plays a critical role in M&A although it often takes only second place to commercial and financial considerations (Huang and Kleiner, 2004).

Table 2: showing the key success factors

KEY SUCCESS FACTORS (KSF)	
SOFT KSF MANAGEMENT TEAM INTELLECTUAL CAPITAL ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE COMMUNICATION	HARD KSF ACQUISITION SEARCH DUE DILIGENCE FINANCIAL RESOURCES INTEGRATION PLAN

Bertoncelj (in press) suggests, based on the study of M&A activity in post-transition economies, that KSF differ in their importance for individual companies, but all aforementioned KSF are considered relevant for the corporate performance. The study also suggests that hard KSF are considered more important than soft KSF to increasing the given amount of subjectivity involved, this is a surprisingly low self-rating. Therefore, the motivation for M&A activity, as well as the strategic value-creators that drive the deals in developed and developing economies is of interest. But how to succeed at an activity in which the odds of success are so slim? Is there a recipe for success?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The researcher would be conducting two research designs for carrying out the research. First, the researcher is using Descriptive style of research design. The main purpose of choosing description style of research design is so that the data collected is very concise & structured and analysis would be factual & simple. The researcher would be collecting data pertaining to Merger & Acquisitions & M & A advisory firms & process. Second, the researcher would be using exploratory research design in a limited format, to conduct interview with top executive and the people who are relevant to the organization, so that the researcher can understand the way the entire process of M & A firm

Area of study

The merger advisors are different and specialized in different task, so to facilitate the study. The author has selected 4 M&A Advisory firms in Bangalore to study in details and rest of the advisory firms are selected from different parts of cities randomly. Finally at the time of analysis the author will include all the feedback of the respondents and the responses of the online survey before coming to the conclusion and giving suggestion

DATA ANALYSIS

Chi-square test

A chi-squared test, also referred to as chi-square test or test, is any statistical hypothesis test in which the sampling distribution of the test statistic is a chi-squared distribution when the null hypothesis is true, or any in which this is asymptotically true, meaning that the sampling distribution (if the null hypothesis is true) can be made to approximate a chi-squared distribution as closely as desired by making the sample size large enough.

$$X^2 = \sum \frac{(\text{Observed frequency} - \text{Expected frequency})^2}{\text{Expected frequency}}$$

With Chi Square, a value is calculated from the data using Chi Square procedures and then compared to a critical value from a Chi Square table with degrees of freedom corresponding to that of the data. If the calculated value is equal to or greater than the critical value (table value), the null hypothesis is rejected. If the calculated value is less than the critical value, the null hypothesis (Ho) is accepted.

Analysis on success of merger and acquisition across kind of business

To determine the difference between success of merger and acquisition across kind of business company operating is significant, the test procedure, called the **two-proportion z-test** was employed.:

Table3: Two-proportion z-test

Status	Banking and Financial services	Others
Success	71.43%	65.57%
Failure	28.57%	34.43%
Z value	1.9410	
1-tail probability	0.1301	
2-tail probability	0.2602	

Since the P-value (0.1301) is greater than the significance level (0.01), we cannot reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the proportion of success of merger and acquisitions not significantly different across kinds of Business Company operating.

Interpretation: From the above results of we can conclude that the process of merger and acquisitions effect on different kind of business is similar in nature means the success and failure rate are approximately equal in all forms of business.

Analysis on effect of Procedure or Handbook In the process of Merger and Acquisitions

Table 4: Spearman's rank correlation coefficient

Spearman's rank correlation coefficient	Success of merger and acquisition	Procedure or handbook to conduct merger and acquisitions
Success of merger and acquisition	1.00	0.80
Procedure or handbook to conduct merger and acquisitions	0.80	1.00

The sign of the Spearman correlation indicates the direction of association between X (the independent variable) and Y (the dependent variable). If Y tends to increase when X increases, the Spearman correlation coefficient is positive. If Y tends to decrease when X increases, the Spearman correlation coefficient is negative. A Spearman correlation of zero indicates that there is no tendency for Y to either increase or decrease when X increases. The Spearman correlation increases in magnitude as X and Y become closer to being perfect monotone functions of each other. When X and Y are perfectly monotonically related, the Spearman correlation coefficient becomes 1.

The sign of the Spearman correlation indicates the direction of association between Success of merger and acquisition Procedure or handbook to conduct merger and acquisitions is positive and it is 0.80 indicating that the Success of merger and acquisition and Procedure or handbook to conduct merger and acquisitions are positively related with each other.

Interpretation: From the above test results we can conclude that the Procedure or handbook in the process of merger and acquisitions has a significant positive effect on the success of the merger and acquisition project.

The Kind of Business where the Companies are Operating

Table:5 Kind of Business Company operating

Attributes	No of firms	Percentage	Chi-square value	p-value
Investment banking	170	44%	82.821	<0.000
Consultancy	100	26%		
Intermediary	60	15%		
Lender	60	15%		
Total	390	100%		

Analysis on Industries where the Majority of Mergers and Acquisitions Operates

Table:6 Industries the majority of M&A OPERATES

Attributes	No of firms	Perc.	Chi-square value(p-value)
Manufacturing	110	28%	96.7550 (0.0001)
Banking and financial services	83	21%	
Computer and information technology	65	16%	
Medicine	42	11%	
Services	40	10%	
Transportation	32	8%	
Educational institutions	28	7%	
Total	400	100%	

Table:7 Analysis on Different kinds of benefits of Mergers and Acquisitions

Attributes	No of firms	Perc.	Chi-square value(p-value)
Efficient Management	140	35%	115.255 (0.0001)
Tax reduction	80	20%	
Talented employees	50	13%	
Proper utilization of resources	40	10%	
Exploration of new market	35	9%	
All the above	55	14%	
Total	400	100%	

Table:8 Factors are responsible for the failure of merger and acquisition

Attributes	No of firms	perc.
Unclear vision	126	32%
Cultural Differences	86	22%
Ineffective Management	65	16%
Integration	40	10%
Workforce factors	39	10%
All the Above	39	10%
Total	395	100%

Attributes	No of firms	Perc.	Chi-square value(p-value)
Candidate screening	205	51%	68.0850 (0.0001)
Stage2 Negotiating and closing	125	31%	
Post merger integration	70	18%	
Total	400	100%	

Analyses on the Benefit of the Merger and Acquisitions

Table:9Benefit the most from M&A

Attributes	No. of firms	Perc.	Chi-square value(p-value)
Acquirer	210	53%	1.000 (0.31)
Acquired	190	48%	
Total	400	100%	

Table:10 The Role Of Merger And Acquisitions Advisory Services

Attributes	No of firms	Perc.	Chi-square value(p-value)
Strategic aspects	120	30%	107.1(0.0001)
Structuring	75	19%	
Defining long term objectives	80	20%	
Clearing on scope and decision making	70	18%	
leadership	55	14%	
Total	400	100%	

Table:11 Factors lead to the success of the project

Attributes	No of firms	Perc.	Chi-square value(p-value)
Clear defined objectives and strategies	57	14%	96.050 (0.0001)
Effective risk management	42	11%	
Human resources	40	10%	
Project manager	27	7%	
Project planning and control	36	9%	
Top management	32	8%	
External environment	31	8%	
Clear communication	27	7%	
Culture	23	6%	

Performance Monitoring	22	6%
Retaining right people for the right place	18	5%
Stakeholders management	16	4%
Time management	13	3%
Cost management	9	2%
Objective management	7	2%
Total	400	100%

Table:12 Problems Faced In Merger and Acquisitions Projects

Attributes	No of firms	Perc.	Chi-square value(p-value)
Clients may have higher expectation	205	52%	30.1243 (0.001)
Not easy to find out proper buyer	70	18%	
Data not available client side	58	15%	
Uncertainty in timing, price and strategy	28	7%	
Allot of work	30	8%	
Total	391	100%	

Table:13 Procedure or handbook to conduct merger and acquisitions

Attributes	No of firms	Percentage	Chi-square value(p-value)
Yes	250	63%	25.000 (0.001)
No	150	38%	
Total	400	100%	

Table:14 The strategy or practice adopted to make the M&A project successful

Attributes	No of firms	Percentage	Chi-square value(p-value)
Showing clear vision	140	35%	107 (0.001)
Guiding	70	18%	
Helping them in financing	60	15%	
Negotiation	50	13%	
Exploring new market	40	10%	
Cooperation	40	10%	
Total	400	100%	

Table:15 M&A ARE Essential for India’s overall development

Attributes	No of firms	Percentage	Chi-square value(p-value)
yes	250	63%	25 (0.001)
no	150	38%	
Total	400	100%	

Table:16 M&A create employment opportunities

	No of firms	Percentage	Chi-square value(p-value)
yes	240	60%	16 (0.001)
no	160	40%	
total	400	100%	

Table:17 M&A CREATE STRATEGIC VALUE FOR THE ORGANISATION

	No of firms	Percentage	Chi-square value(p-value)
yes	190	48%	1 (0.31)
no	210	53%	
total	400	100%	

Table:18 Indian government promote merger and acquisitions

	NO OF FIRMS	Percentage	Chi-square value(p-value)
yes	220	55%	4 (0.045)
no	180	45%	
total	400	100%	

Table:19 Complications are more, in which type of company public or private

	No of firms	Percentage	Chi-square value(p-value)
YES	310	78%	6.986(0.001)
NO	90	23%	
TOTAL	400	100%	

Table:20 M&A will save companies from incurring losses

	No of firms	Percentage	Chi-square value(p-value)
YES	210	53%	1 (0.31)
NO	190	48%	
TOTAL	400	100%	

FINDINGS

- There should be, had book of Instruction what should possessed by all the Merger and Advisory firms to avoid changes.
- Most of the Merger failed because by are not approach by a good and experienced M & A advisory firms And It is also found that, they are not able to have a proper goal, so every organization, first they should understand& recognized the goals.
- Manages should possess knowledge regarding the process.
- M & A should be carefully planned and nothing should be left to chance, failure rate also lies in neglecting the Ingrate approach of balanced management of KSF by managers of acquiring companies.
- There should be a two way communication between management and employees to avoid chaos and to reduce the feeling of insecurity.
- Effetely planning to should be there, plan need to include realistic goals and reasonable time frames and should cover all the key aspects of an organization including people, system and process.
- Retention of talented work force is a Major reason behind the decision of merge, should take the most important priority during the merger process. Management should take the measures to improve the retention rate of the best people in the merging companies.

- Conducting a cultural audit is a useful ways of obtaining useful information about the two companies differing cultures & it allows the Merge Company to take steps.
- Training & development should be provided to senior and Middle Management & should focus on all aspects of the Merges process. Such interventions will facilities effective leadership on the part of the Manager.
- Post Merger integration Team should be set up for the smooth running of all the critical areas of the organization including finance, sales, marketing, HR & operations.
- The project team should not focus on only final deliverable of the project but should focus on the deliver of the desired project which must also be in the efficient & cost effective Manner.
- Involving Mergers & staff and key shareholders in discussions of the vision, values and strategic objective, help on reacting agreement, goal and going commitment to active them.
- CEO should be committed to manage the executive team to be committed to the project & to deal and should not leave in between.
- People Involved in the project must have clearly delegated responsibly & legitimate authority to carry out to responsible task.
- The vision needs to be established project early in the life of a project and it shared between project team.
- Manager should dedicate the time for the employees who participate in project.
- Client must be willing to change according to the project recommendations and should have the organizational leverage to act on the consultants Recommendations.
- Must of the companies hire consultants based on prior performance, experience & few. According to my suggestion, the New & young should also employed to put there New strategies & ideologies for the success factors and also look in to the consultants understanding of the potential client needs should be the criteria.
- There should be consistent procedures and formal Guidelines in the M & advisory firms.
- These should be clear project structure in the organization which is often underestimated and business seek to reserve the integration activity using internal staff sharing their time between the project.

- The successful post transaction integration can active only by having specialist with a experienced internal and external expert with full engagement & sponsorship from senior management.
- The successful post transaction integration can achieve only by having sperfist with a experienced internal and external expert with full Engagement & Sponsorship from Senior Management.
- There should be proper Monitoring and Controlling of the project by the project merger to work with an established data & should keep all the aspects of project within the standards of acceptability of the organization.
- Rewards & recognition play a key role in Managing performance & Motivating Project team.
- Merger decisions is made at a superficial level and are insufficiently researched & with the prospects for success by overestimated. The lack of Market and Technology know can in one being guided too much by one's own wishful thinking.

CONCLUSION

Mergers have been the prime reasons by which companies around the world have been growing, the inorganic route has been adopted by companies forced by immense competition, need to enter new markets, saturation in domestic market thrust to grow big and maximize profits for shareholders. In the changing market scenario it has become very important for firms to maximize wealth for shareholders; many researchers has shown significant findings out of their research

Merger and acquisition are among the most critical decision a ceo can make. Successful merger can create substantial synergies through the combination of complimentary assets and economies of scale and scope. By misguided acquisitions and mergers can lead to over investment in declining industries and misallocation of companies to parents unable to reap their full potential .In addition to these large effect in shareholders in ,a value destructive takeovers can cost the CEO his job.

Hiring financial advisors and consultants may be a competitive move to ensure the highest price for the target firm's shareholders. Relationship may be developed and maintain to obtain specific expertise necessary to ensure for valuation for the shareholders of their firms. All the advisors whether a financial or legal advisors may plat an important role in the negotiation

process. Multiple advisors teams may mitigate the complexity of the deal and boost the shareholders' value

This research study provide to other researcher with valuable study and n insights to the topic of critical success factors for merger and acquisition projects from the perspective of merger and advisory firms. This new success factors and new study on M&A success factors will assist Advisory firms and corporate sector in better achieving success in their M&A Projects. In the meantime our research has some limitations and the most important part is our study aims at exploring the perception of M&A Advisory firms in general which allow us to collect data regarding of the firm's organization as well as their company types. It is impossible to generate a universal checklist of project success criteria suitable for all projects. Success criteria will differ from project to project depending on a number of factors

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